

**Indigenous and plant specific microbial community consortia derived from
phryganic biomes improve plant fitness and soil functions in ecosystem
restoration of quarry deposits in Milos (Greece)**

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Introduction: Quarrying operations cause irreversible damage to the local environment creating vast degradation problems including fertile soil depletion, vegetation removal, and alterations in the original topography. Restoration practitioners aim to restore ecosystem functions by re-installing plants, focusing on recreating specific plant communities based on historical, reference, or desirable output. However, routine restoration interventions often overlook the importance of soil microbial communities and plant-microbe interactions and make poor use of microbiome-based tools. Although, it is well-established that root-associated microbial communities play a pivotal role in plant performance & stress tolerance, support pioneer plant colonizers, and provide crucial ecosystem services, their potential use in soil restoration and rehabilitation remains poorly explored. In this study, we investigated the impact of inoculations with indigenous whole rhizospheric bio-communities on the growth and performance of three drought tolerant native plant species, along with their effects on soil fertility and functions.

Methods: Three indigenous plant species (*Anthyllis hermanniae*, *Calicotome villosa*, *Atriplex halimus*) were sown in pots filled with semi-sterile quarry deposits (bentonite and perlite, 3:2 ratio) and grown in a greenhouse in Milos Island, Greece. Plants were inoculated with whole rhizospheric bio-communities referred to as crude inoculum. Inocula derived from either the natural vegetation of conspecifics (own-crude) or from the pioneer species *Hyparrhenia hirta* (Poaceae) (crude-HH). Inoculations were applied immediately after sowing and again three months after seedling emergence, this time accompanied with an N-based fertilizer application (thiourea 0.01% w/v per pot). After 11 months, plant performance traits, available macronutrient levels [1], potential nitrification rates (PNR) [2], β -glucosidase, β -galactosidase, NAG, and acid/alkaline phosphatase activities were assessed [3]. Response values for each trait were calculated as $\text{Response (\%)} = (T_{\text{Inoc}} - T_{\text{C}}) / T_{\text{C}} \times 100$, where T_{Inoc} is the trait value in the inoculation treatment and T_{C} is the control. Paired-samples t-tests compared mean trait values between inoculation treatments and the corresponding control.

Results: Both legumes exhibited a similar response in response to the inoculation treatments (Fig. 1). In the case of own-crude inoculations without fertilizer, both species displayed significantly elevated root biomass, and number of nodules while they also displayed higher PNR and NAG activity. The positive effects on plant growth performance and soil functions were sustained in the presence of fertilization, although the effect varied between species, as it was more pronounced in *C. villosa*. Interestingly, legumes inoculated with Crude-HH, exhibited higher root biomass, above-ground K concentration and NAG activity in the absence of fertilization. When combined with fertilizer, both species displayed increased number of leaves, NAG, and acid phosphatase activity while the increase

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Figure 1: Response values of the above- and belowground plant traits, available soil nutrients and soil functions to inoculation in the presence and absence of fertilizer N treatments for *A. hermanniae* (a, b, c, d) and *C. villosa* (e, f, g, h). The paired-samples t tests were used to compare the difference in the mean trait values for each inoculation treatment. The horizontal error bars show the 95% confidence intervals for the response values (means \pm 95% confidence intervals). The solid circles represent the significant responses of plant traits to inoculation at $P < 0.05$.

in K content was sustained in above-ground and root K concentration for *C. villosa* and *A. hermanniae* respectively. Regarding *A. halimus* plants, own-crude inoculation increased all plant performance traits, Olsen P, available K, and alkaline phosphatase activity. In the presence of the fertilization, these effects were sustained in above-ground tissues and soil alkaline phosphatase (data not shown). Inoculation with crude-HH, without fertilizer, increased significantly plant height, above-ground potassium concentration, and root biomass. With fertilizer, plant height, above-ground potassium concentration, Olsen P levels, and β -glucosidase activity were significantly enhanced. Overall, we suggest that reintroducing indigenous rhizospheric communities from conspecifics can enhance plant performance traits, potentially leading to the restoration of soil functions. The inocula derived from pioneer species showed positive but inconsistent effects, and notably, did not improve symbiosis in legumes. This promising microbiome-based approach may be further developed and serve as a sustainable, eco-friendly and cost-effective strategy for enhancing revegetation and soil health restoration in barren quarry areas.

Keywords: restoration, quarries, crude microbial inoculation, phryganic biome, indigenous, root-associated microbial community

References

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